
Evaluation of the Nutritional and Medicinal Value of Raw and Fermented *Lagenaria breviflora* Root

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Abstract *Lagenaria breviflora* is a perennial plant that has been used in the antiquity for the treatment and management of diseases and disorders. The general believe of the ancient herbalist was that the plant's leaf, stem and root had good components which was unknown to them for healing purposes. This research focused on the evaluation of the aqueous extracts from the fermented root sample for their antibacterial activity. The proximate and some of the chemical components (phytochemicals) from raw and fermented samples for their edibility and healing purposes. The values obtained for the antibacterial activities were *Shigella* (22.00 ± 0.20), *E. coli* (10.00 ± 0.10), *Salmonella typhi* (20.00 ± 0.10), *Klebsiella pneumonia* (5.00 ± 0.10), *Staphylococcus aureus* (7.00 ± 0.20), *Enterobacter* (No zone) and *proteus* (No zone) respectively. The proximate compositions indicated that Crude Protein was 17.60 ± 0.20 and 18.06 ± 0.20 while the Carbohydrates were 37.19 ± 0.30 and 51.56 ± 0.50 respectively. These two parameters were higher in fermented sample. The phytochemicals quantified for dried raw and fermented samples were Tannin (mg/g) (0.260 ± 0.10 and 0.230 ± 0.20), Phytate (g/100g) (3.430 ± 0.20 and 3.380 ± 0.20), Alkaloid (g/100g) (3.200 ± 0.30 and 2.000 ± 0.20), Oxalate (mg/g) (2.340 ± 0.20 and 2.160 ± 0.20) and Saponin (g/100g) (16.690 ± 0.50 and 13.600 ± 0.20) respectively. These results revealed that the antibacterial activity of the aqueous extract from the root of *Lagenaria breviflora* is good for curative purposes except *Enterobacter* and *proteus*. Higher level of phytochemicals in the raw sample indicated that some of these chemicals have been embedded in the extracted fermented sample for its antibacterial activity effectiveness.

Keywords *Lagenaria breviflora*, root, fermentation, phytochemical, antibacterial

Introduction

Plants such as herbs, shrubs or trees are natural sources of organic chemical on earth, valuable in part or in whole in the treatment and management of diseases and disorders dating back to the prehistoric days [1]. A vast reservoir of medicinal plant abounds mostly in Africa where its limited resource controlled-communities are highly predisposed to disease burdens. A claim of beneficial responses and human reliance on use of herbal remedies persists amongst Africans' large population [2]. Extracts of plants which form the basis for all traditional systems of medicine have been used for the treatment of various diseases as reported by Okwu, 2006. *Lagenaria breviflora* is a seasonal creeping plant of Gourd family found in several African countries [1]. It is used in Africa for a wide range of gastrointestinal disorders and measles in man. Livestock farmers especially poultry rearers use the fruit extract of the plant for the treatment of Newcastle disease and coccidiosis in animals [3] and poultry in many parts of south western Nigeria. Moreover, Sonaiya [3] established that the use of available medicinal plants in the treatment and control of diseases in any local community would help maintain and play significant roles in medical health care

accomplishment in the developing countries. And the medicinal values of these plants lie in their component phytochemicals mostly alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids and phenolic compounds [4] which produce definite physiological actions on the human body. *Lagenaria breviflora* (wild colocynth) is one of those numerous plants with characteristic antibacterial and antiviral herbal remedies in local communities such as Nigeria [5]. It is one of the collections of West Tropical African's fruits, a perennial climber ascending to the forest canopy generally widespread in tropical Africa. It belongs to the family: Cucurbitaceae, genus: *Lagenaria*; and specific epithet: *breviflora* [6]. The leaves are extremely scabrid and sandpapery while the fruits are dark green with creamy blotches, and are ovoid to 9cm long. The plant, and more than ever, the fruit is widely used in traditional medicine in West Africa as a herbal remedy for a wide range of gastrointestinal disorders and the treatment of human measles. Studies had been carried out on the leaves extract [7-8] and fruit extract [9-12]. Onasanwo *et al* [13] also reported its anti-inflammatory properties of the ethanolic extract. Analgesic activity was also measured with its analgesic activity. There were significant inhibition effect in each of the test [14] and others from *Lagenaria breviflora*, for healing purposes, but few or paucity of data were made with respect the efficacy of the root for home remedies and pharmaceutical applications. This study aims at studying the efficacies and potency of the raw and fermented roots of *Lagenaria breviflora* for its proximate composition for human consumption, its phytochemical properties and the extract from the fermented sample for its antimicrobial activities for curative purposes. The objectives are to determine the proximate compositions like moisture content, ash content, crude fat, crude protein, crude fibre and carbohydrate content, phytochemical properties like tannin, phytate, oxalate, Alkaloid and saponin on the flour sample of raw and fermented *Lagenaria breviflora* root for their edibility, determine the antibacterial activity of the aqueous extract from the fermented sample after three days against some pathogenic organisms like *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella*, *proteus spp* and *Enterobacter* and ascertain the potency of the extract against the growth of the tested organisms and effect of fermentation on its root based drugs for pharmaceutical purposes.

Materials and Methods

Collection and of plant material: Root of *Lagenaria breviflora* (gbegbe) was harvested from local farm in Owo town, Owo local government area in Ondo state.

Preparation of plant sample: *Lagenaria breviflora* were manually peeled and chopped into pieces. It was divided into two equal parts, while one part was soaked for three days for proper fermentation before sundried for two weeks, the second part was immediately sundried for a period of two weeks, the two samples were reduced to fine powder with the aid of a mechanical grinder to pass through 40 mesh sieve to increase the surface area for proper analysis. The milled powder samples were collected and stored in glass jars, tightly covered and kept for analysis. The proximate composition was carried out according to AOAC [15] while the Phytochemical procedures used were according to Harbone [16-17].

Antibacterial Activity

Source of Microorganism: *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Proteus* and *Enterobacter* were collected from department of microbiology, Federal Medical Centre Owo, Ondo state of Nigeria.

Sterilization of glass ware: All the glassware used for this study such as Petri dishes, Agar bottle, test tube, conical flask, beakers, pipette and forceps were soaked with detergent and rinsed with water. They were sterilized using hot air oven at a temperature of 120 °C for 2 hours. The wire loop was sterilized by heating it in the blue flame of the bunsen burner until red hot and allowed to cool before using. 95% alcohol was used to swab the work bench area to prevent contamination. The process was carried out aseptically.

Media and Reagent: Nutrient Agar (N.A) and Nutrient broth used were prepared according to manufacturer's instructions and autoclaved at 121°C for 15mins.

Antimicrobial Screening Test: The extracts were tested for their antibacterial properties using the agar – well technique [18]. The assay for antibacterial activities was carried out with *Escherichia coli*, *Shigella*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterobacter*, *Salmonella typhi*, *proteus* and *Klebsiella pneumonia*. Triplicate plates of media for each organism were inoculated with the appropriate suspension of bacteria. Agar well was aseptically made in the media

with a sterile 6.0mm diameter cork borer. The different concentrations of the test solutions of extracts were dispensed (0.5ml) aseptically into the wells. The plates were kept in sterilized inoculation chambers for two hours to facilitate diffusion of solutions. The plates were then inoculated at 37°C for 24 hours for the bacteria. The diameters of the zones of inhibitions of bacteria growth were measured in the plates and the mean value and standard error for each organism was recorded.

Results and Discussion

Results

Table 1: Antibacterial activity of aqueous extract from fermented *Lagenaria breviflora* (Gbegbe root)

Organisms	Activity (mm)
<i>Shigella</i>	22.00±0.20
<i>E. Coli.</i>	10.00±0.10
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	20.00±0.10
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	5.00±0.10
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	7.00 ±0.20
<i>Enterobacter</i>	No zone
<i>proteus</i>	No zone

± SDV of triplicate results

Table 2: Results of the proximate analysis of raw and fermented *Lagenaria breviflora* (Gbegbe root)

Parameters (%)	Raw <i>Lagenaria breviflora</i> ,	F- Fermented <i>Lagenaria breviflora</i>
Moisture content	5.50±0.20	5.00±0.10
Ash Content	2.00±0.10	1.00±0.10
Crude Fat	3.75±0.30	2.88±0.20
Crude Fibre	24.50±0.50	21.50 ±0.30
Crude Protein	17.60±0.20	18.06±0.20
Carbohydrates	47.19 ±0.30	51.56±0.50

Table 3: Phytochemical Analysis of Raw and Fermented *Lagenaria breviflora* (Gbegbe root)

Parameters (%)	Raw <i>Lagenaria breviflora</i> ,	F- Fermented <i>Lagenaria breviflora</i>
Tannin (mg/g)	0.260±0.10	0.230±0.20
Phytate (g/100g)	3.430 ±0.20	3.380±0.20
Alkaloid (g/100g)	3.200±0.30	2.000±0.20
Oxalate (mg/g)	2.340 ±0.20	2.160 ±0.20
Saponin (g/100g)	16.690±0.50	13.600±0.20

± SDV of triplicate results

Discussion

Lagenaria breviflora plant has been employed ethno medicinally as therapeutic cure for a variety of diseases. This has been helpful in correlating its uses traditionally with some of its scientific proven activity like antioxidant, antiulcerogenic, antibacterial and many other activities. The antibacterial activities of the aqueous extract from the fermented *Lagenaria breviflora* obtained were shown in table1. The zone of inhibition in millimeters revealed that *Shigella* has 22.00±0.20mm, *E. coli* (10.00±0.10), *Salmonella typhi* (20.00±0.10), *Klebsiella pneumonia* (5.00±0.10), *Staphylococcus aureus* (7.00 ±0.20), *Enterobacter* and *Proteus* had no zone. These indicated that the extract had potency against *Shigella*, *Salmonella typhi* and *E. coli*. These values were higher than the values obtained by Ibrahim *et al* 2014 for aqueous extract of basella and *Helianthus* for *E. coli* zone of inhibition (1.58 and 1.30) so, the result obtained for *Salmonella typhi* (1.5 and 1.1) for basella and *Helianthus* by Ibrahim *et al* [19] were equally lower than the result obtained for aqueous extract from the fermented *Lagenaria breviflora*. These indicate

its potency in curative purposes against the organisms under test. The values obtained for proximate compositions for raw and fermented root samples were as indicated in table 2. The percentage Moisture content were 5.50 ± 0.20 and 5.00 ± 0.10 . The moisture contents in both were very low and has low significant different and this is applicable in determination of shelf life of food sample. Also, the percentage Ash Content were 2.00 ± 0.10 and 1.00 ± 0.10 respectively. These indicated that mineral composition of raw sample was higher than fermented sample. Crude Fat was 3.75 ± 0.30 and 2.88 ± 0.20 for both samples. The acid value of oil in a sample may be used as a measure of quality and the level of its rancidity if determined. The higher the crude oil in a sample, the higher the probability of its rancidity. Crude fibre was 24.50 ± 0.50 and 21.50 ± 0.30 respectively. This helped in food digestibility and absorptivity of digested food in the colon. The Crude Protein was 17.60 ± 0.20 and 18.06 ± 0.20 while the Carbohydrates were 37.19 ± 0.30 and 51.56 ± 0.50 respectively. Fermentation increased the protein and carbohydrates contents in the sample. Protein is essential for cells functioning and healthy growth. This indicated that higher calorie is released for body building in fermented sample.

Table 3 revealed that the raw and fermented *Lagenaria breviflora* had Tannin (mg/g) 0.260 ± 0.10 and 0.230 ± 0.20 , Phytate (g/100g), 3.430 ± 0.20 and 3.380 ± 0.20 , Alkaloid (g/100g) 3.200 ± 0.30 and 2.000 ± 0.20 , Oxalate (mg/g) 2.340 ± 0.20 and 2.160 ± 0.20 and Saponin (g/100g) 16.690 ± 0.50 and 13.600 ± 0.20 respectively. Generally Fermentation reduced the level of the antioxidants in the fermented sample. This may be advantage to the patient with reaction to higher level of antioxidant and most especially in auto immune hepatic patient. It was reported Balogun *et al* [9-10] to contain saponins of which are triterpenoids, cucurbitacin, cardiac glycosides, flavanoids which may be responsible for the different biological activities. Phytochemicals are the bases for the effectiveness of antibacterial activity of plant materials.

Conclusion

The results obtained for the Antibacterial activity of aqueous extract from fermented *Lagenaria breviflora* (Gbegbe root) indicated that *Shigella*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Salmonella typhi* and *E. coli* were susceptible to the root's aqueous extract for curative purpose. Also, fermentation increased the protein content of the sample for healthy growth and enough energy for body metabolic activities but reduced the phytochemical properties of *Lagenaria breviflora* root. This could be taken into consideration if the consumption of the root itself in large quantity is required or proper dilution of the root extract to check the accumulation of the chemical substances in the body system. Some of the phytochemical properties increased the potency of the extract for its antibacterial activity as indicated in the reduced in values of phytochemicals obtained in the dried fermented sample of *Lagenaria breviflora* root.

Recommendation

Lagenaria breviflora root can be employed to treat the pathogenic orgasms under examination and the level of its safety for consumption can be checked by fermentation to reduce its toxicity effect and increased its efficacy for nutritional composition. More so, increase the potency of the aqueous extract for curative purposes. It is recommended that a proximate analysis should be carried out on the root sample to know its nutritional contribution to human diet.

References

- [1]. Germplasm Resources Information Network (GRIN). 2001. Taxonomy for Plants. Agricultural Research Service, Beltsville Area.
- [2]. Okwu, D.E., (2006). Phytochemicals and vitamin content of indigenous spices of South Eastern Nigeria. *Journal of Sustain Agricultural Environment*, 6:30 – 34.
- [3]. Sonaiya, E.B. (1999). International network for family poultry development: Origins, activities, objectives and visions. In Proc. Workshop on Poultry as a Tool in Poverty Eradication and Promotion of Gender Equality, 22-26 March. Tune Landboskole, Denmark.

- [4]. Hill S.J, Ganellin C.R, Timmerman H, Schwartz J.C, Shankley N.P, Young J.M, Schunack W, Levi R and Haas H.L. (1997). International Union of Pharmacology. XIII. Classification of histamine receptors. *Pharmacology Reviews*, **49**(3):253–278.
- [5]. Tomori, O.A, Saba A.B. and Dada-Adegbola H.O. (2007). Antibacterial activity of ethanolic extract of whole fruit of *Lagenaria breviflora* Robert. *Journal of Animal and Veterinary Advances*, **6**(5): 752-757.
- [6]. Burkil, Entry for *Aristida Adescensious* Linn. (1985). (Family PO-ACEAE) In: The useful plants of West Tropical Africa, volume 1, Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, UK.
- [7]. Adedapo A, Adewuyi T, Sofidiya M. (2013), Phytochemistry, anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities of the aqueous leaf extract of *Lagenaria breviflora* (Curcubitaceae) in Laboratory animals. *The Global Science Gateway*. **61**(1): 281-290.
- [8]. Ajani E.O, Sabiu S, Bamisaye F.A, Adenigba B.V, Awomoyi D.D. (2014), Hepatoprotective and antioxidative effect of ethanolic leaf extract of *Lagenaria breviflora* (bitter melon) on indomethacin-ulcerated rats. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences*. **9**(5): 61-68.
- [9]. Balogun M.E, Ajayi A.F, Oji O.J, Besong E.E, Finbarrs-Bello (2014a). Toxicological and biochemical studies of ethanolic fruit extract of *Adenopus breviflorus* (*Lagenaria breviflora* Robert) in Male Albino Wistar Rats. *American Journal of Phytomedicine and Clinical Therapeutics*. **2**(9): 1112-1123.
- [10]. Balogun M.E, Folawiyo M.A, Besong E.E, Jeje S.O. (2014b). Effect of Ethanolic Fruit Extract of *Adenopus Breviflorus* (*Lagenaria Breviflora* Robert) on Hematological indices in Male Albino Wistar Rats. *Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology Advances*. **4**(11): 501-508.
- [11]. Elujoba A.A, Fell AF, Linley P.A. (1991). Chromatographic and spectroscopic analysis of bound and unbound phenolic acids in *Lagenaria breviflora* fruit. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*. **9**(9): 711-715.
- [12]. Elujoba A.A, Olagbende SO, Adesina SK. (1985). Anti-implantation activity of the fruit of *Lagenaria breviflora*. Robert. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. **13**(3): 281-288.
- [13]. Onasanwo S.A, Saba A.B, Oridupa O.A, Oyagbemi A.A, Owoyele B.V. (2011a). Anti-nociceptive and anti-inflammatory properties of the ethanolic extract of *Lagenaria breviflora* whole fruit in rat and mice. *Niger. J. Physiol. Sci.* **26**(1): 71-76.
- [14]. Onasanwo S.A, Singh N, Saba A.B, Oyagbemi A.A, Oridupa O.A. (2011b). Anti-ulcerogenic and in vitro antioxidant activities of *Lagenaria breviflora* (LB) whole fruit ethanolic extract in laboratory animals. *Pharmacognosy Res.* **3**(1): 2-8.
- [15]. AOAC (2000), Official Methods of Analysis. Association of Official analytical chemist 15th edition, Washington DC, USA.
- [16]. Harbone J.B. (1973), *Phytochemical Methods, B Guide To Modern Technics of Plant Analysis*. Chapman and Hall, London, pg 279-281
- [17]. Harbone S. B. (1983), *Progress in phytochemistry*. Pergamon Press Inc. pg 527-530.
- [18]. Pelczar O. S., & Black, P. (1993). Assay for antibacterial activities using Agar – well technique method. *Internet Journal of Food Safety*, **13**:107-114.
- [19]. Ibrahim T.A, Ajongbolo, K.F., Aladekoyi G. (2014). Phytochemical screening and antimicrobial activity of crude extract of *Basella alba* and *Helianthus annuus* on selected food pathogens. *Journal of microbiology and Biotechnology*. pg 27-31.

